

STUDY OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN INCREASING THE SOCIO-POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITY OF WOMEN

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Abstract. The article presents scientific conclusions and statistical analyzes about the position of women in society and increasing their socio-political and economic activity, as well as the role of foreign experiences in this process, as well as the results of studying foreign experiences. The specific participation, activity, and opportunities of women in the current modern science and new innovative technological sphere have been analyzed based on available sources.

Key words. Women, gender equality, socio-political activity, society, senate, economic activity.

INTRODUCTION

Today's global and regional socio-political situation, internal and external potential threats to the development of national independence make the issue of ensuring social and political stable development of the country, social balance and peace extremely urgent. This issue is closely related to moral security. After all, socio-political stability, spiritual security without peace and tranquility creates difficulties in finding a development strategy in life. "Protection of the constitutional system, sovereignty, territorial integrity of our country from various threats, further strengthening of peace and stability is the main guarantee of all our achievements," says Shavkat Mirziyoev [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The role of intelligent women in ensuring the destiny of the nation and the bright future of the country is extremely important. The French writer Honore de Balzac wrote about this, "The future of the nation is in the hands of mothers." Today, on the basis of many researches, by observing families, in a family where a woman is prudent, tasteful, fair-minded, intelligent, and can properly educate her child by paying attention to it in time, this family has more success.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

During the search for methodological solutions to the problem, it is necessary to increase the socio-political and social activity of women in our country, to create

conditions for them to realize their abilities and opportunities in various fields and sectors, and to ensure that their rights and legal interests are unconditionally respected. It is worth saying once again that extensive work is being done in terms of provision, comprehensive support of motherhood and childhood, as well as strengthening of the family institution.

In the process of increasing the all-round activity of women in society, let's name some urgent problems in the life of our country and society:

These complex problems were brought according to the decree No. PF-5325 signed by the President of our Republic on February 2, 2018:

- there is no targeted support system for women who are in need of help and who are in a difficult social situation, the practice of working individually with unemployed and socially inactive women has not been established, the activity of supporting employment and development of entrepreneurship among women is not organized at the final effective level;
- targeted work on preparing young people for family life, forming a modern exemplary family, strengthening its spiritual and moral foundations and traditional family values is not being carried out, the effectiveness of measures to prevent early marriages, conflict situations and divorces in families is low remains;
- the activities of protection of women's reproductive health are not sufficiently organized, there is no effective system for the prevention and prevention of maternal diseases and perinatal diseases, especially in remote rural areas;
- effective measures are not being taken to prevent offenses and crime among women, the mechanism of increasing the legal culture of women and providing them with legal advice does not meet the requirements of the time;
- large-scale tasks of women's committees do not allow to fully mobilize their strength and capabilities in solving the most important problems of women in the conditions of lack of necessary powers and lack of organizational and state units;
- work on training and retraining of personnel in the field of preparing young people for family life, strengthening the family, preventing conflict situations and divorces has not been organized.

In the last three years (2020-2023), about 20 legal documents aimed at protecting the rights and interests of women were adopted, including 2 laws, 1 presidential decree, 4 presidential decrees, and 13 Cabinet of Ministers decisions. Also, in all ministries and agencies, the activities of the Advisory Council on gender equality issues were established, a commission on issues of ensuring gender equality was established, "The full or partial use of women's labor is prohibited the list of jobs

with unfavorable working conditions" was canceled, the Regulation "On Issuing Protection Warrants, Ensuring Execution and Monitoring of Women Victims of Harassment and Violence" was approved, in more than 6,000 cases, women -girls were given a protection warrant, "Helpline" (1146) service was launched to protect them, www.genkom.uz website was created to popularize the life experience of successful women in Uzbekistan. It is an undeniable fact that women around the world are subjected to various forms of harassment, domestic violence, sexual slavery and other forms of abuse. In Uzbekistan, we often face such sad situations. Struggle against it, protection of rights and interests in this regard, deeper understanding of the scale of this global problem is an urgent issue for all mankind. In this regard, every year on November 25, the International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women is widely celebrated in the world according to the resolution adopted by the UN General Assembly in 2000.

CONCLUSION

Generally speaking, our country is leading the ranks of foreign countries in increasing the socio-political and economic activity of women in society. This can be witnessed through the above statistical data and gender analysis. Of course, one of the effective ways to increase the speed of this process and the scope of reforms is the standardization of legal consciousness and culture and moral-aesthetic norms in society. In this way, it is possible to apply international experiences in local conditions and achieve absolute social equality.

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